

Developing an Educational Personnel Information System

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Abstract

Thinking allows humans to make sense of interpretation, represent or model the world they experience, and to make predictions about that world. It is therefore helpful to an organism with needs, objectives, and desires as it makes plans or otherwise attempts to accomplish those goals and it creates specialized humans. Specialization is when people specialize in one thing or another which they are good at. They are researching all the time in several areas to discover a new thing. Research is a systematic investigation into and study of materials and sources in order to establish facts and reach new conclusions. The main objective of the project is to integrate their biography into the system from which every person can know or gather information. In Bangladesh there are different kinds of highly qualified educational Personnel person who can contribute their research to go ahead this country for bright future. The creation and management of accurate, up-to-date information regarding these Personnel's person is critically important to know. My proposed project introduces their work area, achievements, educational information and much other valuable information. The project helps anyone to motivate themselves to know about these intellectual people and increase their knowledge with various research factors.

Keywords: *Biography, Development, Educational Personnel, Information System, Intellectuals, Interpretation, HTML, PHP*

1. Introduction

The proposed project introduces us to specialized people of different significant sectors to know their basic information. The design and implementation of a comprehensive Personnel's information system and user interface is to build up records through a secure, online interface of specialized people. The system utilizes user authentication, displaying only information necessary for an individual. All data is thoroughly reviewed and validated on the server before actual record alteration occurs. In addition to a user interface, the system plans for Personnel's user interface, allowing users to access information. All data is sorted securely and managed by the administrator. This system provides a simple interface for maintenance of research Personnel's information in the universities of Bangladesh.

In many real-world problems, Personnel knowledge is scarce and in high demand. Frequently, the lack of Personalized leads to misjudgements, errors, wrong operation practices etc. The Internet – and the World Wide Web in particular – has become the ubiquitous platform for

distributing data, information, knowledge and Personalized. The rapid growth of the Web, the evolution of the corresponding technologies as well as the way people tend to rely on Web-based services.

Web-based Educational Personnel Information System can be accessed via the Web, forming a set of Web applications known as Web-based Educational Personnel Information System. Web-based Educational Personnel Information Systems focus mainly on the development of the Personnel system component and pays little attention to the Web site component of the application. When developing Educational Personnel Information Systems, a number of challenges must be surmounted like detection of Personalized, knowledge acquisition and knowledge representation, validation, verification etc.

Research comprises "creative work undertaken on a systematic basis in order to increase the stock of knowledge, including knowledge of humans, culture and society, and the use of this stock of knowledge to devise new applications." It is used to establish or confirm facts, reaffirm the results of previous work, solve new or existing problems, support theorems, or develop new theories. A research project may also be an expansion on past work in the field. To test the validity of instruments, procedures, or experiments, research may replicate elements of prior projects, or the project as a whole. The primary purposes of basic research (as opposed to applied research) are documentation, discovery, interpretation, or the research and development (R&D) of methods and systems for the advancement of human knowledge. Approaches to research depend on epistemologies, which vary considerably both within and between humanities and sciences. There are several forms of research: scientific, humanities, artistic, economic, social, business, marketing, practitioner research etc.

2. Literature Review

Literature review is an analysis of the ability to complete a project successfully, considering legal, economic, technological, scheduling and other factors rather than just diving into a project and hoping for the best. During the Feasibility Study, a variety of 'assessment' methods are undertaken. The outcome of the Feasibility Study is a confirmed solution for implementation. Proposed project contains much information about specialized people which are stored into database. The data will be validated manually and put into database as a content of specialized peoples and momentous places.

Presently information of different specialized or Personnel peoples are scattered in different system can be redundant and collecting relevant information may be very time consuming. May be there are many research people information databases is available. But there is no such website or database where all the Personnel's information can be found in one website.

2.1. Personnel Information System

The Personnel Information system is a Computer based system for maintenance of the Service Registers of individuals in an organization. The details pertaining to personnel, postings, qualifications, departmental tests passed, training attended, family details etc are stored in this

system. Retrieval of information is possible based on any individuals or on collective information grouped by certain categories namely designation, retirement, length of service, place of working etc.[i]

2.2. Personnel Management

Personnel information system the collection of information on its employees stored by an organization. At its most basic such information will usually comprise employees' names and addresses, length of service and attendance, and will be maintained by the PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT department. It is common for this information to be kept separate from pay records (which are usually maintained by the finance department). Until the widespread adoption of computerized databases, many organizations found it difficult to analyse this information for MANPOWER PLANNING purposes; it was instead used mainly to deal with problems relating to individual employees. In addition, such information was not readily available to other management departments. Nor did it generally include information on, for instance, skills and training which production departments, for instance, would find useful. A sophisticated personnel information system will comprise an extensive database capable of retrieval and analysis by all management functions. [ii]

2.3. Personnel Information System (PIS)

Personnel Information System (PIS) maintains the information about employees in, departments like personal, promotional, postings, qualification, awards, incentives, leave etc. that assists an organization in many ways. Web-based solution provides the following information: G2G services allow authorized users of the concerned department to update employees' master and transactional information from time to time from any internet point. G2E services allow the employees of the concerned departments to view their complete details during the Govt. service. Employee has to register once depending on the information furnished by him/her for authentication. After registration, the employee can view the complete details of the restricted information allowed by the Govt. department. [iii]

2.4. Design and Implementation of PIS

This work intends to provide a computer-based system for the maintenance of personnel records of employees in organization. The work addresses limitations identified with manual method of handling personnel records of employees in a firm by providing a better platform to eliminate fraud, corruption, file hiding and misplacement, records falsification, duplication, fragmentation, inconsistencies and other vices attendant with manual method of handling personnel records. The Personnel Information System (PIS) software is a user-friendly package that gives one the fit to accurately monitor employees' records effortlessly. With Personnel Information System (PIS), the personnel records of employees in a firm regardless of their place of assignment are simultaneously integrated and rationalized through the creation of a single system that provides accurate information to all in a time and cost-efficient manner. This software is designed for stand-alone windows environment but has the ability to be networked. The interface is Visual Basic language with the structured query language (SQL). The

implementation of the system will provide speedy retrieval of data as well as enhancing effective and efficient data. [iv]

2.5. CPIS

The scope of the project is to capture employee profiles as well as office profiles in the CPIS database of all the departments, spread over in the entire state of Jammu & Kashmir. It also envisages to keep UpToDate information of employees, when they are promoted, transferred or retired etc. It also aims to assign a unique Employee Identification Number to all the employees for future references. Further this CPIS database can be used for electronic service book and GPF. The implementation of CPIS is a Flagship E-Governance Application of the Govt of Jammu & Kashmir. It gives some thought-provoking ideas to everybody, how to manage personnel information systems in the organization. It is able to give clear cut information about an institution or of an office, how many posts are created and how many staff is deployed. In short, it can give information about the excess or shortage of manpower in a particular office in a click of the mouse. The system automates the existing system to the best of its utility and reduces time consuming process of compiling information, data etc which are required very often the manual to a maximum degree. It also minimizes the errors out of labour intensive and time-consuming processes. [v]

2.6. Personnel Information System Management

The personnel information system management specialist operates and manages field personnel information systems, trains and assist system users, or monitors system activities. Duties for MOS 75F at each level of skill are, Receives, reviews, analyzes, processes, distributes, and maintains personnel information files and supporting documentation. Prepares update cycle control documents and input and transmits to servicing data processing facility. Maintains authorized strength levels, organizational, and systems control files. Executes and monitors automated interface with other automated systems. Monitors status of unresolved errors and initiates required corrective action. Monitors processing of feedback from HQDA and takes necessary corrective action. Monitors performance of systems users. Identifies problems and discrepancies. Provides assistance or refers resolution to superiors. Prepares correspondence and forms in draft and final copy. Posts changes to Army regulations and other publications. Prepares and maintains functional files per marks. [vi]

2.7. Personnel Information System Management

This thesis examines the development of human resource management in three UK public sectors local government, the health service and higher education. The focus of the study is the problem of the lack of use of computerized personnel information systems by personnel specialists to develop the human resource management function. The literature of strategic management, human resource management and the fit between them are reviewed together with the history and the development of personnel systems in the UK. Senior personnel practitioners and their organizations in the three sectors were evaluated with respect to the stage of development of organizational planning and the contribution made by personnel

practitioners using questionnaires, and in-depth interviews. The backgrounds and management styles of the practitioners were examined in order to evaluate their perceptions of: human resource management, computer systems and organizational planning. The degree to which practitioners made use of their computerized information systems for administrative and strategic purposes and the problems they perceived were evaluated in order to judge their degree of evolution from 'traditional personnel practice' to 'human resource management'. The research findings indicated that, although there were a number of significant differences between the three sectors studied, these had little effect when considering the broad issues embedded in the six hypotheses. The evaluation of these hypotheses indicated that the practitioners were making substantial use of their systems for administrative but not for strategic purposes. The number of perceived forces discouraging use and development of computerized personnel information systems was found to outnumber the perceived encouraging forces and were aggregated into a forcefield diagram. Furthermore, it was shown that most practitioners had not yet evolved into proactive human resource managers. Suggestions for 'best practice' with respect to choose, use and development of CPIS are provided. [vii]

2.8. Problem Statement

Information about specialized peoples and places helps viewers to gather knowledge. The knowledge helps to perform research work, to take preparation for admission test or job sector and so on. The historical places inspire to know about our country and help to take decision for traveling. But in current situation it's so tough to find all these types of information in one system within short time. Our proposed system collects all data from different place and arranges the data and keep in one place to collaborate the viewers.

There are many problems that can occur to find information:

- Scattered data
- Bother irrelevant data when searching
- Time consuming task
- Fear to find updated information

3. Design

3.1. Entity Relationship Diagram

Project document contains entity-relationship (ER) diagram which is a specialized graphic that illustrates the interrelationships between entities in a system database.

3.2. Symbols used in this E-R Diagram:

Entity: Entity is a "thing" in the real world with an independent existence. An entity may be an object with a physical existence such as person, car or employee. Entity symbol is as follows

Attribute: Attribute is a particular property that describes the entity. Attribute symbol is

Relationship: Relationship will be several implicit relationships among various entity types whenever an attribute of one entity refers to another entity type some relationship exists. Relationship symbol is:

Key Attributes: An entity type usually has an attribute whose values are distinct for each individual entity in the collection. Such an attribute is called key attribute. Key attribute symbol is as follows

3.3. Individual Table Structure

Table 1: menulist

Field	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra
<u>menuid</u>	int(11)			No		auto_increment
menuname	varchar(50)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
active_status	tinyint(3)			Yes	1	

Table 2: navitem

Field	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra
<u>categoryid</u>	int(10)			No		auto_increment
nav_item_name	varchar(50)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
parent_nav_item_ID	varchar(10)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
mothercatgname	varchar(50)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
active_status	tinyint(3)			No	1	

Table 3: *people_info*

Field	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra
peopleinfoid	int(11)			No		auto_increment
categoryid	int(10)			No		
categoryname	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
name	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
birthdate	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
gender	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
die_date	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
about	text	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
education	longtext	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
achievements	longtext	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
shortcut_info	text	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
contact_info	text	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
profile_pic	varchar(512)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	default_pic.png	
published_status	tinyint(3)			No	1	
information_modified_date	timestamp		ON UPDATE CURRENT_TIMESTAMP	No	CURRENT_TIMESTAMP	

Table 4: *places_info*

Field	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra
placeid	int(10)			No		auto_increment
categoryid	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
categoryname	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
placename	varchar(200)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
about	longtext	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
geography	longtext	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
publish_status	tinyint(3)			No		
profilepic	varchar(500)	latin1_swedish_ci		Yes	NULL	
update time	timestamp		ON UPDATE CURRENT_TIMESTAMP	No	CURRENT_TIMESTAMP	

Table 5: *users*

Field	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra
user_id	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
user_pass	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
user_type	varchar(30)	latin1_swedish_ci		No		
status	tinyint(3)			No	1	

3.4. Entity for ER diagram

Figure 1: Treasury Menu List & Navigation Item

Figure 2: Treasury People Info

Figure 3: Treasury Place Info

Figure 4: Treasury Users

3.5. Entity Relationship Diagram (With Table Structure)

Figure 5: Entity Relationship Diagram

3.6. Data Flow Diagram

A Data Flow Diagram (DFD) is a graphical representation of the "flow" of data through an Information System. A data flow diagram can also be used for the visualization of Data Processing. Our proposed project has admin module which can perform to insert/update/delete all Personnel people and places information.

3.7. Data Flow Diagram Notation

Figure 6: Data Flow Diagram Symbol

3.8. DFD of Admin Authentication and Input Data

Figure 7: DFD of Admin Authentication and Input Data

3.9. Database Design

A database design is a collection of stored data organized in such a way that the data requirements are satisfied by the database. The general objective is to make information access easy, quick, inexpensive and flexible for the user. There are also some specific objectives like controlled redundancy from failure, privacy, security and performance.

A collection of relative records makes up a table. To design and store data to the needed forms database tables are prepared. We have used MySQL DB Storage engine as InnoDB. provides the standard ACID-compliant transaction features, along with foreign key support (Declarative Referential Integrity). Two essential settings for a database are:

- Primary key: - The field that is unique for all the record occurrences.
- Foreign key: - The field used to set relation between tables. Normalization is a technique to avoid redundancy in the tables.

4. Implementation

Implementation is the carrying out, execution, or practice of a plan, a method, or any design for doing something. As such, implementation is the action that must follow any preliminary thinking in order for something to actually happen. In an information technology context, implementation encompasses all the processes involved in getting new software or hardware operating properly in its environment, including installation, configuration, running, testing, and making necessary changes.

4.1. Implementation of the system

My system divided into two panels; the first panel is front panel and other is admin panel.

4.2. Front Panel

Project front panel is the frontend of the project. We discuss every part of front panel of the project.

4.2.1. Home page

A home page or index page has various related meanings to do with websites. It can be used to refer to:

- When the user first opens a web browser, it automatically brings you to this page, which is also sometimes called the start page.
- It most often refers to the initial or main web page of a web site, sometimes called the "front page".
- The web page or local file that automatically loads when a web browser starts or when the browser's "home" button is pressed; this is also called a "home page". The user can specify the URL of the page to be loaded, or alternatively choose e.g. to re-
- A personal web page, for example at a web hosting service or a university web site that typically is stored in the home directory of the user.

The home page contains several parts they are like as:

- Meaningful menu item
- Search options to easily find out the desired information
- Randomly generated Personnel people summary view
- Randomly generated momentous places summary

Screenshot of Home page: [viii]

VEPIS Educational Personnel Information System

[Home](#) [Personnel](#) [Places](#) [About Us](#) [Contact Us](#) [Login](#)

Search people/place by name/profession/speciality

Information about personnel

Dr. Syed Manzoorul Islam [\[View Full Profile\]](#)
Syed Manzoorul Islam is a Bangladeshi academic, writer, novelist, translator, columnist, and critic. He is a professor of English at the University of Dhaka. He has published several collections of short stories and several novels from Dhaka and K....

M. A. Wazed Miah [\[View Full Profile\]](#)
M. A. Wazed Miah (6 February 1942 – 9 May 2009) was a Bangladeshi nuclear scientist, the writer of a number of well-known texts in physics and some political history books, a former Chairman of the

Anisuzzaman [\[View Full Profile\]](#)
Anisuzzaman is a Bangladeshi academic of Bengali literature.

Anisuzzaman was a professor of Bengali at the University of Dhaka. Presently, he is professor emeritus in the same department. He has received the Bangla Academy Award and the Ananda Puraskar for his work in the field of Bengali literature. Anisuzzaman actively participated in all the progressive movements the country has ever witnessed. He had notable contributions in the Language Movement (1952), participated in Mass Uprising (1969), taken part in the War of Liberation (1971) and was the Secretary of Bangladesh Teachers' Association in 1971. Anisuzzaman was involved in the anti-autocracy movement (1990), a plaintiff at the symbolic public trial of a war criminal and was a prosecution witness at the International Crimes' Tribunal set up to try those accused of perpetrating crimes against humanity during the Bangladesh Liberation War.

Kamal Hossain [\[View Full Profile\]](#)
Kamal Hossain is a Bangladeshi jurist, statesman, politician and freedom fighter.

Kamal Hossain is a leading jurist in Bangladesh and has conducted a number of landmark cases, published in various law journals in Bangladesh. In addition he has appeared in several international arbitrations, both as a lawyer and an arbitrator, including acting as an arbitrator in the Iran-United States Claims Tribunal. Hossain is renowned worldwide as a jurist and enjoys a long-standing association with the United Nations. Between 1998 and 2003, he served as the UN Special Rapporteur on Afghanistan. He is a current member of the UN Compensation Commission. He is also currently vice chairman of the International Law Association London, chairman of both the IILAST and South Asian Institute of Advanced Legal and Human Rights Studies (SAILHS), honorary fellow of Notre Dame University Bangladesh and the Institute of Mineral and Petroleum Law, University of Dundee and advisory council member for Transparency International. He has also acted as an observer in various elections around the world.

Professor Mohammad Ali Asgar [\[View Full Profile\]](#)
Dr. Asgar developed a modern magnetism laboratory in the Physics department, BUET, in collaboration with IFFS, Uppsala University, Sweden and formed the Dhaka Material Science Group for developing experimental facilities, training expertise in the

Joined the Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology in 1962, worked as Professor and Head of Physics Department, Dean of Engineering Faculty and Member of the Syndicate, BUET. He was also Professor Rashid Chair, BUET. Dr. Asgar developed a modern magnetism laboratory in the Physics department, BUET, in collaboration with IFFS, Uppsala University, Sweden and formed the Dhaka Material Science Group for developing experimental facilities, training expertise in the field and forming a network with local, regional and international cooperation. The laboratory facilities have been developed to prepare magnetic alloys, ferrites, magnetic thin films, amorphous magnetic materials and nano-structured materials in collaboration with the University of Hanoi, Vietnam, through the support of IFFS. Experimental facilities have been developed jointly with IFFS for the study of primary and secondary intrinsic magnetic properties and structure dependent properties for the basic understanding of co-operative magnetism and the technical magnetization process in different magnetic media and to develop hard, semi-hard and soft magnetic materials for technological applications.

Information about place

Raja Memorial Sculpture [\[Full View\]](#)
Location Dhaka, Bangladesh 23°43'57.17N 90°23'44.47ECoordinates: 23°43'57.17N 90°23'44.47E

Kushtia, Potaakhali [\[Full View\]](#)
This situated in Potaakhali

Jaffara, Bangladesh [\[Full View\]](#)
Jaffara is one of the most attractive tourist assets in Sirhat division. It is about 60 km from Sirhat town and takes two hours drive to reach there. Jaffara is also a scenic spot nearby amidst tea gardens and rare beauty of rolling stones from hills. It is situated besides the river Hari in the lap of hill Shohda.

Figure 8: Screenshot of Home page

4.2.2. Personnel Page

Category page contains specific educational sector-based Personnel's information. Personnel's information covers professor, scientist, doctor etc. User can facilitate below operation

- Specific sector-based list of Personnel's summaries; Ex: Personnel professor information about literature or physics
- Full view option for showing details information of Personnel's
- Scrolling for showing multiple summary data of Personnel's

Screenshot of Category Page: Teacher >> Literature [ix]

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Home Personnel Places About Us Contact Us Login Search people/place by name/profession/speciality Search

Literature

Dr. Syed Manzoorul Islam [View Full Profile]
Syed Manzoorul Islam is a Bangladeshi academic, writer, novelist, translator, columnist, and critic. He is a professor of English at the University of Dhaka. He has published several collections of short stories and several novels from Dhaka and K....

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VEPIS © Amiri, University of South Asia

Figure 9: Screenshot of Category Page : Teacher >> Literature

Screenshot of Category Page: Engineer >> CSE [Full View Option]

VEPIS Educational Personnel Information System

Home Personnel Places About Us Contact Us Login Search people/place by name/profession/speciality Search

Biography

Md. Tamig Uddin Ahmed
CSE
Born: 01 February, 1977, Magura, Bangladesh
Contact: Senior System Analyst, Planning Division, Ministry of Planning, Room #18, Block #13, MoP, Sher-e-Banglanagar, Dhaka - 1207
Mobile No. : 8801711962245
Email: secretarygeneral@bcsbd.org.bd; tomiz20929@yahoo.com

Figure 10: Screenshot of Category Page: Engineer >> CSE [Full View Option]

4.2.3. Places page

Places page contains different historical and eye-catching places of Bangladesh. User can know about different places of our country besides knowing about Personnel's info.

- Full view option for showing details information of places
- Scrolling for showing multiple summary data of places

Screenshot of Places Page: Monument

Figure 11: Screenshot of Places Page: Monument

4.2.4. Search Option

Search option helps user to find out Personnel's information or places information quickly from full system. Search option allows Personnel's name, designation, Personnel area, places name, location etc.

Screenshot of search option with search result

Figure 12: Screenshot of Places Page: Historical [Full View]

4.3. Admin panel

Admin panel requires maintaining all data of the system.

4.3.1. Login page

Login page provides an authentication of user whether the user is used for administrative purpose or not. Administrator can do addition, modification of contents which are used for system.

Screenshot of Admin panel

Admin Pannel LOGIN

User ID : admin

Password :

Login

Home

Figure 13: Screenshot of Admin panel

4.3.2. Admin Panel Home

Admin panel home contains all navigations which can control whole system administration. There are several controls which are given bellow:

- ADD HUMAN PROFILE
- VIEW/EDIT PROFILE
- ADD PLACE
- VIEW/EDIT PLACE
- SIGNOUT

Screenshot of admin home page

ADMIN PANEL

MANAGE AND CHANGE YOUR CONTENT

[HOME](#)

[ADD HUMAN PROFILE](#)

[VIEW/EDIT PROFILE](#)

[ADD PLACE](#)

[VIEW/EDIT PLACE](#)

[SIGN OUT](#)

Figure 14: Screenshot of admin home page

Screenshot of ADD HUMAN PROFILE:

The screenshot shows the 'ADMIN PANEL' interface for adding a human profile. On the left is a sidebar with navigation links: HOME, ADD HUMAN PROFILE (highlighted), VIEW/EDIT PROFILE, ADD PLACE, VIEW/EDIT PLACE, and SIGN OUT. The main content area is titled 'MANAGE AND CHANGE YOUR' and contains the following form fields:

- Category:** A dropdown menu set to 'Doctor'.
- Name:** A text input field with an asterisk indicating it is required.
- Born:** A text input field containing '24 Nov 2015, birthplace'.
- Death:** An empty text input field.
- Gender:** A dropdown menu set to 'Male'.
- About:** A rich text editor with a toolbar (File, Edit, Insert, View, Format, Table, Tools) and a text area containing the letter 'p'.
- Education:** A rich text editor with a toolbar and a text area containing the letter 'p'.
- Achievements:** A rich text editor with a toolbar and an empty text area.

Figure 15: Screenshot of admin home page

Screenshot of VIEW/EDIT Human Profile: Mentioned page contains link of Full view, Edit, remove to perform operation. [x]

ADMIN PANEL

MANAGE AND CHANGE YOUR CONT

HOME

ADD HUMAN PROFILE

VIEW/EDIT PROFILE

ADD PLACE

VIEW/EDIT PLACE

SIGN OUT

Select Category: Scientist Go

Scientist

M A Wazed Miah [View Full Profile] [Edit] [Remove]
M. A. Wazed Miah (6 February 1942 – 9 May 2009) was a Bangladeshi nuclear scientist, the writer of a number of well-known texts in physics and some political history books, a former Chairman of the

Professor A A Mamun [View Full Profile] [Edit] [Remove]
A A Mamun is a Bangladeshi Physicist, a professor of physics at Jahangirnagar University, Dhaka, Bangladesh and a Regular Associate of the International Center for Theoretical Physics, Trieste, Italy. Dr. Mamun has pioneering contribution in compl...

M Anwar Hossain [View Full Profile] [Edit] [Remove]
M. Anwar Hossain is a Bangladeshi Plant Scientist. He is a Professor at the Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology in University of Dhaka. He is known for his research on photosynthesis and the development of the flood-tolerant rice vari...

Figure 16: Screenshot of VIEW/EDIT Human Profile

5. Testing

Testing is a process which is intended to show that a program does what it is intended to do and to discover program defects before it is put in use. To maintain the quality of a system or software, the importance of testing the program cannot be overlooked. It is very essential process of software quality assurance and represents the ultimate review of specification, design, and code development. The results of the test run have been checked for errors, anomalies, or information about the programs nonfunctional attributes. Testing can also provide an objective, independent view of the software to allow the business to appreciate and understand the risks of software implementation. Software testing can be stated as the process of validating and verifying that a computer program/application/product:

- Meets the requirements that guided its design and development
- Works as expected
- Can be implemented with the same characteristics
- Satisfies the needs of stakeholders

The purpose of the system testing is to consider all the likely variations to which it will be suggested and push the systems to limits. The testing process focuses on the logical intervals of the software ensuring that all statements have been tested and on functional interval is conducting tests to uncover errors and ensure that defined input will produce actual results that agree with the required results.

5.1. Objectives

The overall objective is not to find every software bug that exists but also to uncover the situations that negatively impact the user, usability and maintainability. Testing cannot demonstrate that the software is free of defects or that it will behave as specified in every

circumstance. It is always possible that a test that is overlooked may discover further problems with the systems.

The main objectives of testing are-

- Testing is a process of executing a program with the intent of finding an error.
- A good test case is one that has a high probability of finding and undiscovered errors.
- A successful test is one that uncovers an as yet undiscovered error.

The above-mentioned objectives imply a dramatic change in viewpoint. It can be said that a test will not be said successful in which no errors are found. Tests should be designed in a way that they can systematically uncover different classes of errors and to do with a minimum amount of time and effort.

5.2. Methods

In a more traditional model, most of the test execution occurs after the requirements have been defined and the coding process has been completed. There are several testing are viewed in system development life cycle, they are

- White-Box testing
- Black-box testing
- Unit testing
- Integration testing
- System testing
- Acceptance testing
- Alpha testing
- Beta testing

5.2.1. White box testing

White-box testing (also known as clear box testing, glass box testing, and transparent box testing and structural testing) tests internal structures or workings of a program, as opposed to the functionality exposed to the end-user. In white box testing an internal perspective of the system, as well as programming skills, are used to design test cases. The tester chooses inputs to exercise paths through the code and determine the appropriate outputs. This is analogous to testing nodes in a circuit, e.g. in-circuit testing (ICT).

While white-box testing can be applied at the unit, integration and system levels of the software testing process, it is usually done at the unit level. It can test paths within a unit, paths between units during integration, and between subsystems during a system-level test. Though this method of test design can uncover many errors or problems, it might not detect unimplemented parts of the specification or missing requirements.

5.2.2. Black box testing

Black-box testing treats the software as a "black box", examining functionality without any knowledge of internal implementation. The tester is only aware of what the software is supposed to do, not how it does it. Black-box testing methods include: equivalence partitioning, boundary value analysis, all-pairs testing, state transition tables, decision table testing, fuzz testing, model-based testing, use case testing, exploratory testing and specification-based testing.

5.2.3. Unit testing

Unit testing, also known as component testing refers to tests that verify the functionality of a specific section of code, usually at the function level. In an object-oriented environment, this is usually at the class level, and the minimal unit tests include the constructors and destructors. These types of tests are usually written by developers as they work on code (white-box style), to ensure that the specific function is working as expected. One function might have multiple tests, to catch corner cases or other branches in the code. Unit testing alone cannot verify the functionality of a piece of software, but rather is used to assure that the building blocks the software uses work independently of each other.

5.3. System Testing Results

For our system we conduct both white box testing and black box testing. By white box testing we test the code, the loops and internal logics, whether they perform correctly or not. And by black box testing we test our system's user interface by providing inputs and examining outputs.

5.3.1. Login testing for admin

Login is successful held by correct username and password. System detects user type from given username.

Figure 17: Screenshot of Login window

Figure 18: Screenshot if user provided credential is successful

Figure 19: Screenshot If user provided credential is failed

5.4. Add Human Profile Testing

Providing all information about Personnel person's in the add form and validate all information and store into database. It also checks duplicity for redundancy [xi]

Figure 20: Screenshot of add human profile with information

5.5. Result After Testing

All information is successfully stored.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `admin/index.php?categoryname=CSE&pageID=editProfile`. The page title is "ADMIN PANEL" and the main heading is "MANAGE AN". On the left, there is a navigation menu with links: HOME, ADD HUMAN PROFILE, VIEW/EDIT PROFILE, ADD PLACE, VIEW/EDIT PLACE, and SIGN OUT. The main content area shows a "Select Category" dropdown set to "CSE" with a "Go" button. Below this, there are two profile entries under the "CSE" category:

- Dr. Mohammad Kaykobad** [View Full Profile] [Edit] [Remove]

Mohammad Kaykobad is a computer scientist, educator, author and columnist from Bangladesh. Along with Muhammed Zafar Iqbal, he started the national mathematics olympiad. Kaykobad is also a pioneer in introducing Science Olympiad organized by Banglades...

Education: Ph.D, 1988; M.Engg., Computer Applications Technology, 1980-82; M.S (Hons) in Engg., Automated Management of Merchant Marine, 1973-79

Interest: Do research in the field of algorithms, computational complexity and optimization

Books: Information Technology Management for ICMA students, Brain twister: Delightful Mathematics

Research Reports: Minimum connection time and some related complexity problems, Regression with minimum absolute deviations, Development of a Bangla Speller

Research Area: Algorithms and Theory
- Dr. Muhammed Zafar Iqbal** [View Full Profile] [Edit] [Remove]

Muhammed Zafar Iqbal is a Bangladeshi author of science fiction and children's literature. He is a professor of computer science and engineering and also head of the department of electrical and electronics engineering at Shahjalal University of Scie...

Education: PhD in Physics from University of Washington

Alma mater: University of Dhaka, University of Washington

Occupation: Physicist, writer, columnist

Awards: Bangla Academy Award (2004)

Figure 21: Result After Testing

5.6. View/ Edit Human Profile Testing

Edit all information about Personnel people in the edit form and validate all information and update into database. It also checks duplicity for redundancy. Screenshot of full view of specific Personnel's profile. [xii, xiii]

The screenshot shows the "ADMIN PANEL" with the heading "MANAGE AND CHANGE YOUR CONTENT". The left navigation menu is the same as in Figure 21. The main content area shows the "Biography" section for "Dr. Mohammad Kaykobad" with the following details:

- Dr. Mohammad Kaykobad** [Edit] [Remove]
- CSE**
- Born:** May 01, 1954 Bangladesh
- Contact:** Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology, Dhaka-1000, Bangladesh
- Email:** mkbd1234@yahoo.com, kaykobad@cse.buet.ac.bd

About Him : Mohammad Kaykobad is a computer scientist, educator, author and columnist from Bangladesh. Along with Muhammed Zafar Iqbal, he started the national mathematics olympiad. Kaykobad is also a pioneer in introducing Science Olympiad organized by Bangladesh Academy of Sciences and Informatics Olympiad in Bangladesh. He wrote a number of books on recreational mathematics. Currently he is a professor of Computer Science and Engineering in Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology. He was a visiting

Figure 22: Personnel's profile

Screenshot of edit human profile: [xiv]

Figure 23: Screenshot of edit human profile

5.7. Result After Testing

All information is successfully stored. [xv]

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `admin/index.php?categoryname=CSE&pageID=editProfile`. The page title is "ADMIN PANEL" and the main heading is "MANAGE AN". On the left, there is a navigation menu with links: HOME, ADD HUMAN PROFILE, VIEW/EDIT PROFILE, ADD PLACE, VIEW/EDIT PLACE, and SIGN OUT. The main content area has a "Select Category:" dropdown menu set to "CSE" and a "Go" button. Below this, there are two profile cards for the "CSE" category. The first card is for Dr. Mohammad Kaykobad, with a photo and text: "Mohammad Kaykobad is a computer scientist, educator, author and columnist from Bangladesh. Along with Muhammed Zafar Iqbal, he started the national mathematics olympiad. Kaykobad is also a pioneer in introducing Science Olympiad organized by Banglades...". His education includes Ph.D. (1988) and M.Engg. (1980-82) from Computer Applications Technology, and M.S. (Hons) in Engg. from Automated Management of Merchant Marine (1973-79). His interests are in algorithms, computational complexity, and optimization. His books include "Information Technology Management for ICMA students" and "Brain twister: Delightful Mathematics". His research reports focus on minimum connection time and complexity problems, and regression with minimum absolute deviations. His research area is Algorithms and Theory. The second card is for Dr. Muhammed Zafar Iqbal, with a photo and text: "Muhammed Zafar Iqbal is a Bangladeshi author of science fiction and children's literature. He is a professor of computer science and engineering and also head of the department of electrical and electronics engineering at Shahjalal University of Scie...". His education includes a Ph.D. in Physics from the University of Washington. His alma mater is the University of Dhaka and the University of Washington. His occupation is Physicist, writer, and columnist. He received the Bangla Academy Award in 2004.

Figure 24: Result After Testing

6. Conclusion

This paper assists in designing a website which contains up to date information of the Personnel people of Bangladesh and in integrating their biography in system and from which every people can know or gather information about them. It can be monitored and controlled remotely. It provides accurate information always. All years together gathered information can be saved and can be accessed at any time. The data which is stored in the repository helps in taking intelligent decisions by the management. So, it is better to have a Web based Information Management system. All the visitors and the users can get the required information without delay. Besides all of this visitor can gather knowledge about different momentous places.

Finally, the whole system has been tested to ensure that everything functions correctly before the system processes actual data and produces information that users rely on. It was quite challenging to improve Development of Web-based Educational Personnel Information System. During the testing of the implementation, it was found that the system was working fine and that our implementation of the system was working better. This project goal is to design and implement the Development of Web-based Educational Personnel Information System was successful and the functionality implemented by us was working satisfactory.

6.1. Project Limitations

This project is only a humble to satisfy the needs of users. The main focus of this project is to lessen user's effort. This project hopes that the system can serve the general needs of visitors/users. Nevertheless, due to the limited time and manpower of this project could not gather all the Personnel's' information in all aspects. Consequently, it can only be used to get the information about few educational Personnel's. In the system there is absence of feedback and interactions among visitors. The dynamic management functions for supporting users are yet to be improved. All these factors might affect the efficiency of use

6.2. Future Work

Technology is changing every day. To cope with this changing environment system should be updated. Probing deeper, the demo system in this project provides a strong foundation for future work. The result has led us to realize that there is still scope for improvement in spite of the fact it has shown appropriateness in Development of Web-based Educational Personnel Information System. Several plans may have been taken for the future work:

- Auto update information
- Notify subscribed people about update information
- Visitor's information will be stored in the database.
- The Personnel's personal web page

New ideas of what more to improve or how to improve the system and what kind of new features to add, come up through the development of project. During the process of implementation, wonderful ideas have been got and hopefully in a near future, there is a possibility and time allocated to improve the system. The survey data will serve as the reference and basis for the further improvements of this system. We may carry out further research and investigation for extend the system to a more powerful in future.

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